

Synthesis of 2-Substituted-phenyl-3-aryl-4-oxo-4H-1,3-benzoxazines as Possible Antifertility/CNS Active Agents

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Twelve new 2-substituted phenyl-3-aryl-4-oxo-4H-1,3-benzoxazines have been synthesised and screened for their toxicity, antifertility and CNS activities. These compounds exhibited antifertility activity upto 50% at the dose levels studied and were found to possess mild CNS effects as well.

1,3-BENZOXAZINES have been reported to exhibit diverse biological activities such as sedative¹, hypnotic², antifertility³, ovicidal⁴, analgesic⁵ and antiinflammatory^{6,7} activities. Further, a survey of the literature⁸⁻¹⁰ on antifertility agents reveals that compounds based on the triphenylethylene and triphenylethane framework possess high antifertility action. Based on these observations the authors have synthesised a number of 2-substituted-phenyl-3-aryl-4-oxo-4H-1,3-benzoxazines (4a-1) in order to evaluate their biological activities. The precursors which (3a and 3b) were synthesised by following an improved method, originally described by Horrum and Zaugg¹¹, were allowed to react with an aryl chloride in the presence of triethylamine in benzene to obtain the final products (4a-1).

Biological testing :

Antifertility activity : Method of Kamboj *et al.*¹², was followed. Two compounds 4h (R=H, R₁=CF₃ and Ar=3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl) and 4i (R=H, R₁=CF₃ and Ar=4-CF₃ phenyl) were found to have 50% anti-implantation activity. Activity in the rest of the compounds ranged between 17 to 43%.

Toxicity studies : Method of Horn¹³ was used. The approximate LD₅₀ (ALD₅₀) along with confidence limit was read out from the Table given in the method. ALD₅₀ of 3a and 3b was found to be >1000 mg/kg i.p., and ALD₅₀ of 4a-1 was in the range of 681 to >1000 mg/kg i.p.

CNS activity : During the toxicity studies compounds were also observed for their effects on gross behaviour according to the procedure of Turner *et al.*¹⁴. At higher doses a decrease in SMA and reactivity was observed.

The compounds were studied at 1/5th ALD₅₀ for their anticonvulsant activity in mice using supra-maximal electroshock seizure test and Metrazole seizure threshold test according to the method of

Swinyard *et al.*¹⁵. They were also studied for antireserpine activity and anorexigenic activity using the method described by Dua¹⁶. None of these compounds was found to possess any significant activity.

Experimental

The reactions have been followed by tlc. Melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 infracord and a Perkin-Elmer 177 or 337 Grating instruments.

2-Substituted phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1,3-benzoxazines (3a and 3b) : A mixture of salicylamide (0.03 mol),

TABLE 1—2-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL-3-AROYL-4-OXO-4H-1,3-BENZOXAZINES (4)

Compd. 4	R	R ₁	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)		
							O	H	N
a	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	Phenyl	58-59	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₃	70.92 (70.95)	4.90 (4.88)	8.60 (8.59)
b	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	4-OF ₃ -Phenyl	186-88	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ F ₃ NO ₃	68.00 (68.01)	3.90 (3.98)	8.01 (8.06)
c	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	3,4,5-Trimethoxy- phenyl	168-65	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ NO ₃	65.10 (65.18)	5.19 (5.21)	2.90 (2.92)
d	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	4-Chlorophenyl	188-40	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClNO ₃	65.12 (65.17)	4.21 (4.25)	8.27 (8.30)
e	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	4-Methoxyphenyl	115	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₃	68.69 (68.78)	4.98 (5.01)	8.81 (8.84)
f	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	4-Nitrophenyl	166-68	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₅	69.57 (68.59)	4.12 (4.14)	6.41 (6.45)
g	H	CF ₃	Phenyl	190-91	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ F ₃ NO ₃	66.42 (66.49)	3.49 (3.52)	3.49 (3.52)
h	H	CF ₃	3,4,5-Trimethoxy- phenyl	99-100	90	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ F ₃ NO ₃	61.58 (61.60)	4.08 (4.10)	2.88 (2.87)
i	H	CF ₃	4-Methoxyphenyl	198-200	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ F ₃ NO ₃	64.61 (64.68)	3.70 (3.74)	3.25 (3.27)
j	H	CF ₃	4-Chlorophenyl	189-85	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClF ₃ NO ₃	61.11 (61.18)	2.99 (3.01)	3.20 (3.24)
k	H	CF ₃	4-Nitrophenyl	266	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ F ₃ N ₂ O ₅	59.69 (59.72)	2.91 (2.94)	6.29 (6.38)
l	H	CF ₃	4-OF ₃ -Phenyl	209-10	96	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ F ₃ NO ₃	59.81 (59.95)	2.71 (2.79)	2.98 (3.01)

aromatic aldehyde (0.03 mol) and 2 drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ was refluxed in dry benzene for 6-10 h in a flask fitted with the Dean and Stark arrangement. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate on cooling yielded the product in pure form.

2-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1,3-benzoxazine 3a: Yield 63%, m.p. 167-8° (Found: C, 67.30; H, 5.22; N, 4.88. C₁₈H₁₅NO₃ calcd. C, 67.36; H, 5.26; N, 4.91%). $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1140 (OCH₃), 1600 (C₆H₅), 1680 (C=O), 2950 (CH₃) and 3200 cm⁻¹ (NH).

2-(4-Trifluoromethyl phenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1,3-benzoxazine 3b: Yield 80%, m.p. 238° (Found: C, 61.40; H, 3.39; N, 4.85. C₁₈H₁₁F₃NO₃ calcd. C, 61.43; H, 3.41; N, 4.78%). $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1075, 1120 and 1160 (CF₃), 1600 (C₆H₅), 1690 (C=O), 2900 (CH₃) and 3300 cm⁻¹ (NH).

2-Substituted phenyl-3-aryl-4-oxo-4H-1,3-benzoxazines (4a-l, Table 1):

A mixture of a benzoxazine (3a/3b; 0.002 mol), aryl chloride (0.002 mol) and triethylamine (0.003 mol) was refluxed in dry benzene for 3-4 h. Triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off. Organic layer was washed first with aqueous NaHCO₃ (5%) and then with water, and finally dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue was recrystallised from ethanol. The products were characterised by their m.p.s, elemental analyses and ir spectra which showed disappearance of the band for NH at 3300-

3200 cm⁻¹ and appearance of a band at 1780 cm⁻¹ for imidocarbonyl group.

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